

The Impact of Bank Staff Stress on Banking Performance in Nepal

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between stress among bank staff and the overall performance of Nepal's banking sector. As financial services expand quickly and competition increases in the Nepalese banking industry, staff face heavy workloads, strict deadlines, and higher customer expectations. These stressors can negatively affect productivity, service quality, and organizational efficiency. The main goal of this research is to evaluate the levels and sources of occupational stress among bank employees and to analyze how it impacts key performance indicators like customer satisfaction, employee retention, and financial results.

Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 210 banking professionals across public and private sector banks in Nepal using a self-administered questionnaire. The survey included measures of job stress, organizational performance, and demographic variables. The preliminary findings indicate a significant negative correlation between high stress levels and performance outcomes. Key stress factors identified include long working hours, inadequate managerial support, and insufficient career development opportunities. Additionally, female employees and front line staff reported higher stress levels than their counterparts.

These findings highlight the importance of effective stress management programs, leadership development, and policy changes to improve employee well-being and maintain organizational performance. The implications of this study are crucial for HR policy reform, leadership training, and creating a supportive work environment in the Nepalese banking sector.

Keywords: *banking performance, employee well-being, job stress, organizational efficiency, stress management survey research*